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Roughness who?

Sebastiano Trevisani
Dept. Culture del Progetto
University Iuav of Venice,
Venice, Italy
strevisani@iuav.it

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Abstract—This abstract presents some of the topics of the author’s keynote at the Geomorphometry 2025 conference. Some intricacies, ephemerality and controversial concepts concerning the characterization of surface texture are discussed. Surface texture in earth sciences and ecology is most often referred to as surface roughness or surface ruggedness, even if many other related terms are adopted. Starting from ambiguities in the concepts and terminology other key aspects are discussed. One central theme, sometime forgotten despite self-evidence, is that the conventional raster representation of topography provides a representation of apparent roughness. Another key point is related to the generalization or smoothing of digital elevation models, and more in general to the decomposition of the topographic signal in different components of spatial variability. Then a crucial and difficult aspect is related to the need to create a repository of benchmark surface textures, fundamental to describe, compare and test surface roughness metrics. Unlike surface metrology and image texture analysis, the creation of collections of reference textures is a difficult task given the complex spatial-statistical characteristics of analyzed morphologies. Some key aspects of surface texture characterization are pointed out by means of the analysis of different landscapes. The purpose of the talk is not to propose the “right” terminology or the best recipes for roughness characterization. The main objective is to highlight the complexity of the topic, the variety of purposes and applications concerning surface roughness, and the many cross-contaminations with other disciplines, such as surface metrology and image analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Surface roughness (SR) is a key concept in multiple fields of sciences and engineering, including earth sciences and ecology, showing an increasing interest in the last decades [1–8]. Surface “roughness”, similarly to “ruggedness”, is one of those buzzwords in earth sciences and ecology that many researchers use and compute with some related metric, generally having an intuitive idea of its meaning but without having or providing a clear definition of it. Even though the analysis of SR related metrics

returns relevant information concerning the geoenvironmental factors and processes being studied or modelled, there are evident ambiguities in SR definition, computation and application among different disciplines and scholars. These ambiguities, even if unavoidable to some extent, should be mitigated or at least the controversial aspects should be pointed out. In geomorphometry there is a lack of consensus [1,2,9] on a definition of SR. Multiple related terms are adopted, such as “fabric”, “ruggedness”, “rugosity”, “texture”, “waviness” and others (e.g., [10–12]). Some authors describe SR as a metric related to surface (or “topographic”, “terrain”, etc.) “complexity”, inheriting all the fuzziness (and complexity!) related to term “complexity”. Is a horizontal surface with some fine-grain roughness more complex than a smooth folded quadratic surface? Most of the popular computed SR indexes are relatively simple measures of surface spatial variability and are not capable of providing real information on complexity. Complexity of topography is not just variability in general terms; an expression of complexity can be for example the coalescence of morphological features with multiple wavelengths or the presence of complex curvilinear spatial patterns. From a geostatistical perspective [13], SR indexes are related to the spatial statistical variability structure of surfaces, so a wide range of indexes related to the morphological spatial patterns can be envisioned. Probably, referring to “surface texture” (ST) is more intuitive even if still with some fuzziness. But at least ST permits to use an intuitive concept related to human perception (visual and tactile) and also to analogous approaches adopted in metrology and computer vision [14–17]. Intuitively, ST may imply the presence of some repetitive pattern; however, this implication is not mandatory and sometime singular and not repetitive patterns are very distinctive elements of topographic signature [10]. Hereinafter, the term SR is intended as a synonym of ST and hence something referring to the overall spatial variability structure of surfaces. Accordingly, SR is intended differently from the surface metrology discipline, where roughness is considered a short-range aspect of ST. However, also in surface metrology there is an

unavoidable ambiguity related to the scale of analysis with respect to the scale of morphological features analyzed (e.g., when does roughness become waviness?). The use in this talk of SR as synonym of ST is related to the fact that many works using the keywords surface “roughness” or surface “ruggedness” are referring to the wider concept of surface texture more than to “surface roughness” as intended in surface metrology.

II. SOME KEY POINTS

A. Signal decomposition

The concept of signal decomposition in different components of spatial variability is a key step in geomorphometric analysis, including ST analysis. This step underlays many algorithms for the computation of basic land surface parameters (LSPs), such as slope and curvatures [18]. Every time a quadratic surface is fitted to the data to compute a LSP, this implies the smoothing of the DEM via local polynomial of order 2. Even when computing LSPs parameters without fitting quadratic functions, just using discrete partial derivatives, many authors smooth the DEM before computation. Another example is represented by the generalization of DEM required for calculating LSPs from the perspective of physical based geomorphometry and landscape segmentation [19]. The generalization or regularization of the surface is a well-known concept in geostatistics [20], where the signal is generally decomposed in two components, the trend, the deterministic/structured component, and the random part, generally representing fine-scale morphology (from which the roughness is generally evaluated). Both components are interesting and serve different purposes. Unfortunately, the decomposition between the two is not univocal and contributes to the complexity of many DEM preprocessing steps. This is the case of “residual topographies” derived subtracting from the original DEM a generalized/regularized/smoothed version of it. In the “residual topographies” we find a wide range of terms such as topographic position index (TPI), relative position, residual DEM, residual relief, detrended surface, etc. [21,22] Apart from very simple situations, there is no best way to split the signal in the two components; moreover we are not limited to a dual representation. This is because of the complexity of real surfaces and also in relation to the different approaches that can be used for generalization. In fact, in addition to the selection of the level of generalization, there are many approaches, essentially convolutions, that can be adopted to generalize the DEM, such as: single pass moving averages, multi-pass moving averages, moving medians, gaussian kernels, local polynomials, and others. The decomposition of the signal is relatively simple if one has in mind the range of wavelengths of the features to be highlighted (e.g., the granulometry of the gravel of a riverbed) and if this range does not change too much from place to place. But in general, given the characteristics of real topographies, it is better to adopt multiscale approaches considering different levels of generalization. At the end it is a matter of dispersion variance [20]. Considering for

simplicity a smoothing based on moving average (i.e., a local polynomial of order 0 or a convolution with a square wave), the bigger the window is more spatial variability is filtered out, leaving features with longer wavelengths in the smoothed DEM. Conversely, the complementary part of the signal is represented in the residual topography. In addition, analogously to what is performed with wavelets analysis, differentiating different levels of DEM generalization is possible to isolate specific wavelengths (or frequencies in the frequency domain).

B. Overtreatment?

There are various efforts toward the creation of improved SR indexes and the comparison of the existing ones. However, for a variety of reasons, the way forward isn't smooth and there are open questions to be addressed. Some questions are the typical ones related to the standardization and benchmarking of metrics: according to which cost function the metrics should be evaluated? With respect to which benchmark data sets? And, more importantly, better according to which purpose? These are central questions for comparing existent ST indexes and for creating new ones. However, on top of this, we need also to consider how real surfaces are represented digitally. The way in which we sample/measure a real surface and represent it digitally affects the fidelity in surface spatial variability reproduction. Dealing with measures of spatial variability, two key aspects need special care: 1) sampling spatial density and 2) measurement spatial support. The two interlinked aspects affect spatial variability, both from the perspective of Nyquist-Shannon sampling theorem and from the perspective of dispersion variance [20]. Let's focus on the widespread representation of surfaces on a regular grid, i.e. a raster DEM, which is essentially a 2D representation obtained projecting a 3D surface onto a horizontal (at least locally) surface. This kind of representation has some characteristics to consider when computing spatial variability indexes. For example, for a DEM with a projected coordinate system the maximum sampling density is along the cardinal directions and the lowest along the diagonals. This should be clearly considered when computing lag dependent indexes such as topographic ruggedness index (TRI), radial roughness index (RRI) and other geostatistical approaches [9,23]. This aspect is more challenging when dealing with DEMs in geographical coordinates, given the latitude dependent spacing along longitude [24]. A key aspect is that we are dealing with an apparent roughness and in general to a morphology as seen “from above”; the true surface morphology is lost and cannot be retrieved, except without formulating restrictive assumptions on its characteristics. Given this biased representation on topography, one should always ask to which extent push forward the efforts for improving SR metrics. For example, is it worth extending the RRI to increments of order 3 or more to filter out more complex local trends, when at the end what we want to describe is inherently flawed?

On another perspective, it is difficult to state what makes a metric a proper measure of SR, especially when this is intended in

the general sense of ST (e.g., [25]). Considering the definition of SR limited to fine-grain spatial variability, the characteristics of a proper index are relatively easy to be defined: it should be positive, independent from the structural component of spatial variability (local slope for sure, but what about curvature?), it should measure the variability of the surface considering small distances between pixels, it should use enough samples and based on a robust estimator (if you don't want to highlight outliers). Considering the wider concept of ST, the definition of metric properties can be trickier; for example, it could not be mandatory to assure the positiveness of a ST index.

C. Reference datasets

A compact plain language definition of texture is: “the way that something feels when you touch it” (Britannica dictionary). Accordingly, texture (of a surface or of an image) is something related to the object but also to the observer. For example, the ST is perceived differently if we are touching a surface with a finger or with the palm of the hand, or if one person has tiny or big fingers. The fact that surface and image texture are a perceptive property implies some observer subjectivity. If we ask people to segment an hillshade or a residual topography according to ST, different individuals will perform different segmentations, at least if we don't consider very simple topographies with very distinct domains of ST. In fact, the presence of coalescent multiscale morphological spatial patterns creates many difficulties in creating benchmarking/references datasets such as labelled subdomains with specific surface textures.

In surface metrology the surfaces have often rhythmic spatial structures, and the textures are relatively simple in terms of spatial patterns, in addition to a well-defined genesis. For example, the standard sets for comparing roughness instruments are relatively simple. Also, in the context of image analysis generally the textures analyzed are relatively simple and repetitive. However, earth and planetary morphologies are often much more complex, with coalescent multiscale structures, sometimes multifractal, and nonstationary in the spatial-statistical sense. One specific aspect of nonstationarity is represented by spatial discontinuity, manifested by abrupt morphological transitions like hot spots, lineaments and sharp variations from one textural domain to another. Sometime these are present in repetitive spatial patterns and sometimes are just singular distinctive features in the landscape. These discontinuous features have a special significance both for interpretation as well as for the impact on the calculation of spatial variability indexes, especially when using non-robust estimators. Accordingly, to create collections of “archetypes” of surface textures for benchmarking purposes, like in surface metrology and image analysis, we need to isolate specific patterns of ST (e.g., Fig. 1). This makes sense intuitively; however, which kind of rules should we follow to create this collection of surface textures?

Figure 1. Example of a mosaic of different real surface textures, represented with a hillshade (512 x 512 pixels, resolution 2 m)

A complementary solution is also the creation of synthetic surfaces, because these permit to control the properties of surfaces, isolate specific aspects and mimic also the impact of the different digital representations.

D. Complex morphological patterns

Even if there are important differences in the main conventional and less conventional SR indexes some of these can be highly correlated especially when considering small search windows. In fact, most of the popular indexes convey similar information, being relatively simple measures of variability of local morphology. The point is that, thinking to the complexity of surface textures (Fig. 2) and to the different purposes of “roughness analysis”, there is the need of indexes capable to detect specific aspects at specific scales. For example, anisotropy in short range-roughness is one of them, but other interesting indexes to be developed could highlight asymmetric and curvilinear features. In addition, the metrics should be designed in relation to the application (e.g., analysis of ecological connectivity, impedance to flow, etc.). Accordingly, in most morphological settings to describe ST just one index isn't enough (or at least a single scalar property) and multiscale approaches should be adopted.

III. CONCLUSIONS

There is still a lot of work to be done on many fronts: a) persevere in exploiting the cross-contaminations with other related fields, e.g., surface metrology and image analysis, including pattern recognition [16,17]; b) try to find a consensus on terminology and definitions; c) Create benchmark datasets of surface textures (real and synthetic) for testing, comparing and benchmarking algorithms; d) develop indexes tailored to highlight specific patterns and to specific tasks; e) clarify interconnections between different approaches and with the morphogenetic processes.

Figure 2. Example of a complex landscape from the perspective of surface texture (projected Copernicus DEM, 30 m, UTM zone 38N, Mauritania desert)

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